

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF MODERN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TRAINING

KHOREZMSCIENCE.UZ

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UDC: 37, 37.09, 377

PREPARING STUDENTS TO DEVELOP STUDENTS’ MOTIVATION TO LEARN THROUGH THE SUBJECT OF “INTRODUCTION TO A SPECIALTY”

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Annotatsiya. “Mutaxassislikka kirish” fani orqali talabalarni o‘quvchilarning bilim olishga bo‘lgan qiziqishini oshirish – bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarni kasbiy-pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlashda muhim o‘rin tutadi. Mazkur maqolada ushbu fanning o‘qish motivatsiyasini rivojlantirishga ta’sir etuvchi usullari va pedagogik mexanizmlari tahlil qilingan. Ta’lim jarayonida o‘quvchilarning kasbiy yo‘naltirishga nisbatan qiziqishlarini shakllantirishda samarali pedagogik yondashuvlar va ularni rag‘batlantirishning amaliy vositalari muhokama qilingan. Maqolada, shuningdek, o‘qish motivatsiyasini kuchaytirish uchun ta’lim jarayonida zamonaviy texnologiyalarni qo‘llashning ahamiyati ta’kidlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: “Mutaxassislikka kirish”, o‘quv motivatsiyasi, pedagogik mexanizm, kasbiy ta’lim, zamonaviy texnologiya, pedagogik yondashuv, o‘quv jarayoni, kasbiy yo‘naltirish, ijtimoiy motivatsiya, ta’lim samaradorligi, amaliy vositalar.

Аннотация. Повышение интереса студентов к обучению посредством предмета «Введение в специальность» играет важную роль в подготовке будущих учителей к профессионально-педагогической деятельности. В статье анализируются методы и педагогические механизмы данного предмета, влияющие на развитие учебной мотивации. Обсуждались эффективные педагогические подходы и практические средства мотивации студентов к развитию интереса к профориентации в процессе обучения. В статье также подчеркивается важность использования современных

технологий в образовательном процессе для повышения мотивации к обучению.

Ключевые слова: “Поступление на специальность,” мотивация обучения, педагогический механизм, профессиональное образование, современные технологии, педагогический подход, образовательный процесс, профориентация, социальная мотивация, эффективность обучения, практический инструментарий.

Abstract. Increasing students’ interest in learning through the subject of “Introduction to a Specialization” plays an important role in preparing future teachers for professional and pedagogical activities. This article analyzes the methods and pedagogical mechanisms of this subject that affect the development of motivation to learn. Effective pedagogical approaches to forming students’ interest in professional orientation in the educational process and practical means of stimulating them are discussed. The article also emphasizes the importance of using modern technologies in the educational process to enhance motivation to learn.

Keywords: “Entry into specialization,” learning motivation, pedagogical mechanism, vocational education, modern technology, pedagogical approach, educational process, vocational guidance, social motivation, educational effectiveness, practical tools.

Introduction

The subject “Introduction to a specialty” plays an important role in increasing the motivation of future teachers to study and developing their interest in professional orientation. Through this subject, students gain a complete understanding of professional activities and specialties, and their interest and motivation for studying are strengthened in themselves. The article analyzes the introduction of students to methods and pedagogical approaches to developing students’ motivation to study through the subject “Introduction to a specialty.” The effectiveness of the use of modern technologies, interactive methods, practical exercises, and pedagogical mechanisms in the educational process is discussed in this direction. The subject “Introduction to a specialty” serves to develop students’ professional adaptation and active motivation. The main goal of this process is to provide students with basic concepts and knowledge of the profession or field they have chosen, and to develop professional skills in them. To achieve this goal, the various methods and technologies used by future educators in the educational process are of great importance.

Literature Review

In the subject of “Introduction to a Specialty”, pedagogical approaches given to students occupy a special place. Future educators should develop educational strategies that are suitable for them, taking into account the personal characteristics of students and their attitude to learning. In this process, it is necessary to use active and effective methods aimed at forming motivation, as well as take into account the personal needs and interests of students [1, 2].

Modern educational technologies create great opportunities for the effective organization of the educational process and increasing student motivation. In the process of teaching the subject “Introduction to a Specialty,” students’ interest in learning is increased by using interactive technologies, distance learning platforms, virtual laboratories, simulations and other information technologies. For example, online video lessons, presentations and multimedia materials make the learning process lively and interesting. Information technologies ensure active participation in the learning process, encourage students to contribute to the learning process. At the same time, interactive exercises help develop students’ thinking skills [3, 4].

Practical training based on professional orientation helps prepare future teachers for their future professional activities. Through these trainings, students develop the skills necessary to perform tasks related to future work. Also, through practical training, students get acquainted with various situations in professional activities and acquire skills aimed at solving them. Through the subject “Introduction to a specialty”, students gain knowledge about the great role of encouragement in increasing students’ motivation to study, and that by encouraging students, their interest and enthusiasm for studying increase. Future teachers can encourage students to study by recognizing their achievements, giving them positive evaluations, and involving them in various contests and competitions. There are various forms of encouragement. For example, for students to achieve good results, they can be given various gifts, certificates of commendation, and also highlighting their achievements in front of other students. Through such approaches, students' interest and enthusiasm for learning increases, and their attitude towards the learning process changes in a positive direction [5-7].

Research Methodology

The article discusses several methods and pedagogical mechanisms that influence learning motivation, such as the use of modern technologies, interactive methods, and practical exercises. These methods help increase students’ engagement and interest in the educational process. The subject also contributes to professional adaptation by developing students’ knowledge, skills, and enthusiasm for teaching.

Analysis and Result

The subject “Introduction to a specialty” is important in developing students’ social motivation through students. Social motivation is a person’s need and interest in establishing relationships with other people and cooperating with a team. By motivating students socially, it is possible to increase their interest in the learning process. To increase students’ social motivation, future teachers need to organize group exercises, group work, and activities aimed at forming strong social ties. For example, by involving students in working in groups and encouraging them to participate in various projects, they develop their skills in working with a team and their interest in learning.

Using a personal approach in teaching the subject “Introduction to a Specialty” is also one of the effective methods for increasing student motivation. Through a personal approach, prospective students develop appropriate educational strategies, taking into account the personal needs, interests, and abilities of students. This increases students’ interest and motivation in learning. A personal approach helps students actively

participate in the learning process, encourages them to contribute to the learning process. Also, through a personal approach, it is possible to identify students' problems in the learning process and take measures to solve them. This serves to increase students' interest and motivation in learning. Teaching the subject "Introduction to a Specialty" helps prospective teachers effectively establish pedagogical dialogue and strong relationships with students. Through pedagogical communication, students' interest in the learning process increases, their active participation in the learning process is ensured. Teachers should establish effective communication with students, fully answer their questions, listen to their opinions and support them.

Strong relationships serve to increase students' enthusiasm for the learning process. Future teachers can increase students' interest in learning by establishing trusting relationships with students and encouraging them in the learning process. This helps students to actively participate in the learning process and increase their enthusiasm for their chosen profession. In order to develop students' motivation in the subject of entering a specialty, it is important to use strong guidance and decisive approaches in the educational process. Strong guidance ensures that students clearly define their goals in the learning process and take the necessary measures to achieve them. This helps to increase students' interest and enthusiasm for learning. Through the critical role of the educational process, students are ensured to understand their responsibilities in the learning process, actively participate in the learning process, and strive to apply their knowledge in practice. This helps to increase students' interest in learning and strengthen their professional aspirations.

Innovative approaches and project activities also help higher education students develop their motivation to study by teaching the subject "Introduction to a Specialty." Through project activities, students conduct independent research on topics of their choice and have the opportunity to implement various ideas. This helps to develop their interest in the learning process and creative abilities. Innovative approaches make the educational process interesting and effective. For example, involving students in virtual excursions and conducting research using modern information technologies increases their interest in studying. Also, innovative approaches strengthen students' preparation for professional activities and form practical skills in them.

The importance of technology in the modern educational process is great. The use of modern information technologies in teaching the subject "Introduction to a Specialty" serves as an important factor in increasing students' motivation to study. In particular, Saidov I.K. noted that electronic educational resources and virtual laboratories help to arouse students' interest and revitalize their activities. Through these technologies, students will have the opportunity to receive information that is easy to learn and interesting. Pedagogical approaches used in teaching introductory subjects play a major role in determining the professional direction of students. Salimov N.Y. emphasizes in his study that effective pedagogical dialogue between teachers and students is important in increasing students' professional motivation [5]. This dialogue helps students to actively participate in the learning process and increase their interest in their profession. The social environment plays a great role in developing students' professional motivation by future teachers. Social environments such as family, community, and educational institution play an important role in

students' professional development. Normatov Sh.M. noted that the social environment and family environment are important in shaping students' interest in studying and their attitude to the profession [6]. Therefore, parents and teachers play an important role in supporting students. The subject "Introduction to a specialty" is one of the main factors in ensuring the professional development of higher education students. In particular, Rakhimov F.A. noted that teaching subjects focused on the specialty has a positive effect on the professional development of students and prepares them for future success [7]. At the same time, the subject "Introduction to a specialty" helps students' professional development.

Conclusions

The subject "Introduction to a specialty" serves as a necessary factor in developing students' interest in their professional direction and, through this, students' motivation to study. This subject ensures that future teachers actively participate in the professional education process and increase their enthusiasm for their chosen profession.

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UDC: 37, 780.7

CONTENT AND PEDAGOGICAL NECESSITY OF "TRADITION" CONCEPT IN THE STUDY OF TRADITIONAL SINGING

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida pedagogika sohasi oliy ta'lim tashkilotlari musiqa ta'limi yo'nalishida "An'anaviy xonandalik" fanini o'qitishning pedagogik zarurati, an'ana, xonandalik, ashula tushunchalari mazmuni va o'qitishning kasbiy va pedagogik imkoniyatlari muhokama etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *musiqa, ashula, xonandalik, ijrochilik, pedagogika, pedagogik zarurat, kasbiy musiqa, ta'lim, tushuncha, an'ana, an'anaviy xonandalik.*

Аннотация. в данной статье рассматривается педагогическая необходимость преподавания предмета "Традиционное пение," содержание